

Managing Editor's Column

Vol. 31, No. 4

Dear Readers,

It gives me great pleasure to announce the third regular issue of 2025. I would like to thank all the authors for their sound research and the editorial board and guest reviewers for the extremely valuable reviews and suggestions for improvement. These contributions together with the support of the community enable us to run our journal and maintain its quality.

I would still like to expand our editorial board: If you are a tenured associate professor or above with a good publication record, please apply to join our editorial board. We are also interested in high-quality proposals for special issues on new topics and emerging trends.

In this regular issue, I am very pleased to present 5 accepted papers by 19 authors from 6 countries: Algeria, Argentina, Bangladesh, India, United Kingdom, and Vietnam.

In the first paper Neha Kumari and Rajeev Kumar from India address improvements of compiler error messages in the context of wildcard-type argument inference in Java programs by additions to the current wildcard-based type inference algorithm to get detailed and valuable error messages. Liliana Favre from Argentina discusses research on a unified formal framework for metamodeling in the context of MDE, which is based on the Nereus metamodeling language and includes transformers for translating MOF metamodels to Nereus metamodels and Nereus metamodels to MOF metamodels. In their joint work between researchers from Vietnam and the UK, Phan Minh Nhat, Ngo Le Huy Hien, Dinh Minh Toan, Le Viet Hung, Phan Binh, Phung Thi Anh, Nguyen Thi Hoang Phuong, and Nguyen Van Hieu introduce their research on detecting concentrations by Near Infrared Reflectance Spectroscopy (NIR) in cattle and poultry fertilizers by a synthesized machine learning model named EBAR (Error Based Accumulation Regression) combined with a backward elimination technique designed to identify crucial wavelength ranges for monitoring component concentrations. In another collaborative research between Algeria and India, Maroua Benleulmi, Ibtissem Gasmi, Nabiha Azizi, and Nilanjan Dey present an overview of deep learning-based recommender systems, explore their application to enhance performance, and discuss their limitations. Last but not least, Mahir Shadid, Mushfiqus Salehin Afnan, Rashed Mustafa, and M. Jamshed Alam Patwary from Bangladesh highlight their research on a multimodal fusion algorithm for non-intrusive anxiety detection based on TI-Fusion, a multimodal fusion technique that integrates text and image data for a unified reliable outcome and overcomes the limitations of other existing methods.

Enjoy Reading!

Best regards,

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'Christian Gütl', with a stylized flourish at the end.

Christian Gütl, Managing Editor-in-Chief
Graz University of Technology, Graz, Austria
Email: c.guetl@tugraz.at